

App Micontrol

Introduction

This operational group pursues to manage the regulation of the mycological resource through tools based on Information and Communication Technologies (ICT), guaranteeing sustainability in the use of the mycological resource, traceability in the value chain and offering useful information to both the collector and the business sector. One of the problems identified in the mycological sector is related to the difficulty of harvesting control tasks

Approach and main results

As an innovative solution, GO Mikogest has developed the Micontrol app, designed to facilitate the work of harvest control of the guards in the mycological areas. In addition, it captures data on the development of the harvesting activity through the quantities collected and yields by species with socioeconomic interest. This application has two objectives: - Facilitate the management of the environmental agent in the control of harvesting in his task of verifying that the activity is carried out according to the conditions of collection established in the enclosure. - Capture data of the harvesting activity. The app has been designed to be used by multiple users through any model of mobile device. A web space has also been developed for each user, from which they can manage the data of all their inspections, visualize them through GIS technology, access their images and verify the data of each inspection. The application has two different functionalities: 1-Control of harvesting activity: With the harvesting control, it is verified that the activity is carried out according to the harvesting conditions established in the enclosure. The environmental agents carry out the inspection activity to the collectors, verifying that they have authorization (license) and that they respect harvestable species, sizes and quantities, being able to carry out the pertinent proceedings for the processing of complaints if the situation requires it. 2- Inspection Manager: Micontrol is a manager of inspections carried out, which facilitates and organizes the work done in the field by the agents. The capture of the collector's personal data can be done manually, or through the capture of this data by means of a QR reader, which speeds up and prevents the data entered from being erroneous. This QR reader is only valid for enclosures that include this code in their harvesting permit. In addition, through the micontrol app, the rural guard, private field guard or civil guard-seprona, verifies in real time (with mobile coverage) fraud by falsification of harvesting permits. This functionality is only available for certain reserves, integrated in the Micocyl mycological exploitation system.

The application sends a query to the database receiving a valid or unmatched permit message. The activity of harvesting control generates a very important volume of data about the harvesting that is being carried out in the territory. Micontrol enables a simple system for the capture and management of this data, contemplating the different scenarios faced by the agent in his control activity.

Lessons learned

The digital skills of the people who carry out the collection control are highly variable, so it is advisable that the data capture app has a very simple design that is easily understood by less digitally skilled users. It is important that any control that is performed on a collector takes as little time as possible, so that the use of this application is both attractive and convenient. If the monitoring process involves lengthy data collection over time, it may reduce interest in using the application.

The information presented in this factsheet was developed by the FOREST4EU partner, drawing on the innovations and knowledge generated by the indicated operational group with their explicit authorization.

Further information

<https://www.mikogest.net/pagina/micontrol>

montse.ganado@cesefor.com

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